

1 **Supplementary materials**

2 **Supplementary material 1.** Responses to categories of demographic questions collapsed to

3 avoid model complete separation.

Questions and category	Collapsed category
Farming experience	
0 – 2 years	Less than 10 years
3 – 5 years	
5 – 7 years	
7 – 9 years	
10 or more years	10 or more years
On-farm role	
Employee	Not owner
Family member	
Manager	
Other	
Owner	Owner
Age	
< 20 yrs	< 40 years
20 – 29 yrs	
30 – 39 yrs	
40 – 49 yrs	40 – 59 years
50 – 59 yrs	
60 – 69 yrs	≥ 60 years
> 70 yrs	
Highest education	
Did not go to high school	Did not finish high school
8th grade	
Some high school	

Completed high school	Completed high school/apprenticeship training/trade school
Completed apprenticeship training or trade school	
Some college or university	
Completed bachelor's degree at a college or university	At least went to college/university
Completed a graduate degree (e.g., Master's degree)	
Completed professional degree	
Number of cows milked per day	
Small	< 250 cows
Medium	250 – 499 cows
Large	≥ 500 cows
Breed of milking herds	
Holstein	Holstein
Jersey	Others
Other	
Housing of milking herds	
Free stall barn	Free stall barn
Tie stall barn	Tie stall barn
Bedded pack	Others
Other	
Milking system	
Parlor	Parlor
Pipe-line	Pipe-line
Robotic	Others
Other	
Percent of dairy animals bred with beef sires/semen	
0%	0%
1-25%	1-25%

26-50%

51-75%

>25%

76-100%

5 **Supplementary material 2.** Demographics and farm characteristics of responded dairy producers

Characteristics (n = 315 for each)	Response frequency (percentage)
State	
Florida	13 (4.1%)
Michigan	39 (12.4%)
Ohio	67 (21.3%)
Vermont	50 (15.9%)
Wisconsin	59 (18.7%)
N/A ^a	87 (27.6%)
Farming experience	
0 – 2 years	4 (1.3%)
3 – 5 years	7 (2.2%)
5 – 7 years	5 (1.6%)
7 – 9 years	8 (2.5%)
10 or more years	289 (91.7%)
N/A ^a	2 (0.6%)
On-farm role	
Employee	2 (0.6%)
Family member	16 (5.1%)
Manager	15 (4.8%)

Owner	277 (87.9%)
Others	–
N/A ^a	5 (1.6%)
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Age	
< 20 years	3 (1.0%)
20 – 29 years	15 (4.8%)
30 – 39 years	45 (14.3%)
40 – 49 years	62 (19.7%)
50 – 59 years	69 (21.9%)
60 – 69 years	77 (24.4%)
> 70 years	40 (12.7%)
N/A ^a	4 (1.3%)
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Highest education	
Did not go to high school	4 (1.4%)
8th grade	18 (5.7%)
Some high school	33 (10.5%)
Completed high school	90 (28.6%)
Completed apprenticeship training or trade school	19 (6.0%)
Some college or university	43 (13.7%)
Completed bachelor's degree at a college or university	53 (16.8%)
Completed a graduate degree (e.g., Master's degree)	9 (2.9%)

Completed professional degree	7 (2.2%)
N/A ^a	39 (12.4%)
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Number of cows milked per day (median \pm interquartile range)	86.5 \pm 68 cows
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Breed of milking herds	
Holstein	242 (76.8%)
Jersey	38 (12.1%)
Others	27 (8.6%)
N/A ^a	8 (2.5%)
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Housing of milking herds	
Bedded pack	31 (9.8%)
Free stall barn	169 (53.7%)
Tie stall barn	92 (29.2%)
Others	16 (5.1%)
N/A ^a	7 (2.2%)
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Milking system	
Parlor	146 (46.3%)
Pipe-line	97 (30.8%)
Robotic	20 (6.3%)
Others	43 (13.7%)
N/A ^a	9 (2.9%)
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Producing organic milk		
Yes		46 (14.6%)
No		263 (83.5%)
N/A ^a		6 (1.9%)
Frequency of veterinary visits		
Weekly		26 (8.3%)
Every 2 weeks		49 (15.6%)
Every 3 weeks		–
Monthly		100 (31.7%)
Every 2 months		18 (5.7%)
Less frequent than every 2 months		16 (5.1%)
No regular visit		100 (31.7%)
N/A ^a		6 (1.9%)
Calves taken care by farm employees		
Yes		107 (34.0%)
No		193 (61.3%)
N/A ^a		15 (4.8%)

6 ^aN/A = not available

7 **Supplementary material 3.** Cramér's V correlation matrix of the demographic of dairy producers

	Farming exp	Role	Age	Education	Herd size	Breed	Housing	Milking system	Organic	Male calf age at sale	Calf care by employees	State	Percent bred by beef sires/semen
Farming exp		0.08	0.4	0.3	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.02	0.13	0.17	0.08	0.24	0.14
Role			0.27	0.02	0.16	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.06	0.08	0.04	0.15	0.04
Age				0.28	0.06	0.04	0.1	0.15	0.21	0.17	0.18	0.15	0.09
Education					0.27	0.12	0.25	0.19	0.22	0.16	0.33	0.34	0.11
Herd size						0.2	0.27	0.33	0.19	0.62	0.54	0.36	0.19
Breed							0.29	0.07	0.29	0.09	0.09	0.32	0.08
Housing								0.5	0.26	0.11	0.32	0.28	0.11
Milking system									0.11	0.17	0.35	0.33	0.14
Organic										0.15	0.08	0.22	0.13
Male calf age at sale											0.16	0.20	0.12
Calf care by employees												0.26	0.09
State													0.14

8 Cramér's V > 0.25 represents a strong correlation (bold)